

LEADERSHIP AND ITS STRATEGIC FUNCTIONS IN THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to show the effects of leadership's strategy and coordination unity on the organization. Another element of strategic leadership is to shape and shape it by foreseeing the future.

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Because in order to prevent the risks that may occur in the future, the organization must always be well disciplined and organized. In this direction, if they create a strategic management understanding well and empower the employees in this regard while empowering them, and most importantly, by directing creative and innovative goals, they can provide strategic differences quickly and at the highest level expected from a bad and more complex global competitive environment. Strategic leadership is to consider the goals and capabilities of the organization as a whole and to ensure that the organization demonstrates its power to fight between the known reality and unknown possibilities in the best way, and to maintain its continuity and integrity by adhering to all its values and principles. Because they provide these, they do their best to make the connection between the current vision and mission and even future plans stronger. Leadership builds a bridge between the present and the future in achieving the goals of the organization, and this bridge should be used in order to achieve a good future by providing the best management in terms of structural, social and all abilities. Only in this way, the desire of the organization can contribute to its success.

Keywords: *leadership, strategy, global competition*

abstract

1.1.STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP THEORIES

The strategic leadership theory has emerged from the top-level theory, and the fairy organizations of strategic leadership are seen as a reflection of the CEOs. Strategic leadership was also seen as a mystery, and many strategic leadership tasks alone accepted their problems. In this respect, the basic duties and responsibilities of the strategies of the organizations, which have a strategic leader, are to determine a vision for the organizations and to achieve this vision in the best way. It is to create the vision in the best possible way, under the best conditions that can create its name. To give an example, these elections resulted in financial success. Key leaders depict a distinct prowess and superiority of companies. In addition, with this developing technology and globalization brought by the 21st century, the stagnant and predictable position of organizations. Environmental conditions have changed dramatically. While industry and change in the past century have been linear, key competitors are mostly local rather than global. The organization that can best reveal the competitive structure with these has proven that the strategic leaders are successful. The companies, organizations and institutions that prove the success in this competition stage have achieved success behind a good strategic leadership organization. Those who cannot keep up with the competitive market, which has none of these, and remain behind are organizationally unsuccessful. Because they have not achieved good strategic leadership. It is necessary to determine a good vision for a well-coordinated organizational structure. There are features that strategic leaders should have and combined with their responsibilities, which draw attention in all the literature. As leaders strategically, senior managers have an important responsibility, which is to coordinate all functions of the organization, all objectives, all goals and plans, and to keep the climate in the organization neutral by taking this responsibility.

2.1. STRATEGY ROAD STAGES OF ORGANIZATIONAL LEADERSHIP

Employees in the organization see the strategic leader as a guide and they move forward in the chart that he has drawn with him. Strategic leadership is the top layer that contains very important functions in this regard. The leader's vision, which has emerged within the organization, must be a good study of the activities. However, in some organizations, intra-organizational conflicts between these functions can create a new perspective. This new perspective is not a situation that occurs only among the employees within the organization, not according to the leader of the organization, it is a poison ivy that takes over the organization completely. Because, as it is known, poison ivy wraps everywhere and is known to start in a small place. Likewise, in conflicts, it starts between one or two people and can take over the entire organization. One of the most important duties of leaders who will say in such cases is to be a good coordinator and a good mediator. It is best for him and the organization to have the leader hypnotize his own analytical thoughts well.

2.2. EFFECTS OF LEADER & BEHAVIORS ON THE ORGANIZATION

The leader always sets an example for the employees of the organization with his behaviors and manners and actions and becomes a source of inspiration for the employees of the organization. Over time, the stance of its leaders is discussed and the organization adopts the character structures on itself. To talk about three characteristics, strategic leadership usually tries hard to create high performance standards, but these efforts may not always be successful. Because there are many risks in the market, however, there are businesses with a better organizational structure in better conditions than the competition in the serious circles of the organization. In such cases, if he manages to minimize the risk and overcome it in the best way, it always leaves a more permanent effect. There are many tasks undertaken by the leader here. In addition to these duties, the coaching role also plays. There is a team and the best person to lead this team is a strategic leader. This means the coach of an organization. In order for strategic leadership to be managed effectively, it must first establish the vision and mission very well. While these two functions may work well, they support it with a more successful strategic action. These successful strategic activities are examined in two groups. One of these is the good creation of the strategies and the second is the best implementation of the created strategy, and the good progress of both ensures the highest level of strategic competitiveness, which in both cases adds to the success of the organization.

2.3. MISSION FACT BASICS OF STRATEGIC LEADERS

Strategic leadership is best known for managing its own time and that of other units. The important always gives priority, if something that is not important is very urgent, knowing this, he can provide a

solution by saying a responsibility to someone else. At the same time, one of the characteristics of strategic leaders is to be transparent and explanatory, to cooperate with the employees and to establish a healthier environment in order to create a healthier environment. It ensures that the competition within the organization is in an appropriate position. A good strategic leader is responsible for preventing the competition within the organization causing gossip and fighting and providing a fair solution in the best way possible. At the same time, the leader should give confidence. He should have a reliable structure along with his candid speech to the employees. It is one of its most basic features that it is always focused on quality and efficiency. Here it is necessary to create a leader form that can constantly be improved. Thus, it is necessary to increase its education on the internet and to have a curious structure in terms of a constant search, not to be brought up with the methods it is used in, and to learn the best. Good leadership can also be achieved by The most important thing is that the team is fair when solving their problems, and the manager takes place in the system. The leader, on the other hand, used a sentence saying that he is above the system and stated that the manager is in the system, but the leader carries out his duty with more responsibility. This proves how important a word is in the management of today's organizations.

2.4.HOW SHOULD THE LEADER BE A DEVELOPER IN THE ORGANIZATION?

The leader should not reveal himself to the subordinates with his ego or rude attitude. Because if you want to be a good leader, it should never be clear who is the leader when looking at the organization. It is always necessary to act together with flexible behaviors and developer and motivation. The needs of the employees should be met and the direction in which the plans were created should be examined directly. If there's an idea that doesn't make sense, wouldn't it be better if he/she advises to develop that idea or something like this? It is necessary to reinforce the research with non-offensive words such as First of all, the job description should be created very well and the organization should keep what is among the employees of the organization at a good level. It emphasizes that leaders should never have doubts and distances between employees and should try to compromise with them on this issue. A standoff between employees and a suspicion lowers motivation. It increases the fight, destroys the unity within the organization, and the individual whose leadership position is famous cannot be well coordinated and realistic goals should be chosen. Plans should not be created based on dreams based on goals that never exist, and efforts should be made based on goals that can be realized. There should never be competition that can create friction. Of course, competition is very important within the organization. However, a competition that can increase motivation is good. But if there is a competition that causes fights and gossip, this is not good among the employees within the organization. It should invite the organization to cooperation and it should always be known with honesty, reliability and openness. He fulfills his responsibilities and must follow the people he gives responsibility very well. In behavior management, the leader of the organization must respect the basic personality of the people,

the most important of the internal characteristics of the character, which has a strategic structure, and the employees must know how to rest very well. When employees say something to themselves, they need to establish eye contact very well, they need to make one-to-one eye contact with the person speaking, and they need to make this work motivation offensive by being busy with another job while listening, and they need to listen patiently during the conversation and give advice and suggestions without being hurtful. . As I said before, when looking at an organization, if it is never known who the leader is, it shows that it is a really successful organizational structure. It is necessary to establish the sentences well and to listen to the narrations of the other person well, to lead with a good charismatic tone, to gain the motivation and dignity of the employees by themselves and to form the body language very well. These are strategic leadership behavior management. Of course, there are a few more suggestions related to these as well. Although employees are always known for their work, they also expect something from the institution. Because they expect something from the places where they work. These are bonus incentives or a trip to increase motivation and so on. Aid is included in these. If a good strategic leader rewards successful employees, they can increase their motivation even more. Because an employee who can get a good return for his work will be happier and try to be more productive for the company. This is one of the best elements for the organization. At the same time, although strategic leaders are very well organized and able to coordinate, they can sometimes remain surrounded by competition and its environment. It is an advantage for them to be problem-solving and result-oriented in order to minimize these and solve the negativities that may occur in the best way.

The mission has a great importance in the management of organizations. The vision environment is a factor that helps the creation of the analysis, sales planning, and the negative sides of the companies can be observed more than the positive sides in environmental factors. These are problems that may occur in competition conditions, loss of competitive advantage and other threats. In such a case, it is necessary to consider strategic opportunities. Good completion of job duties and organization is important for the environmental analysis of the organization. Otherwise, if a shaped strategic element occurs, the negative effects of environmental analysis will play a role in shaping a bad strategy in terms of organizational. For this reason, a good screening of the environment is a very important element.

In order for organizational cultures to be fully formed, the definition of the environment and what is called environmental should be analyzed and added as critical items to strategic planning. Being well-known and competitive may cause decreases in the market, as well as conflicts within the organization.

3.1. MISSION & MISSION OF THE ORGANIZATION

Stopping the mission and progress of the organization completely and going backwards will completely reduce the motivation of the employees of the organization. For this reason, an organization that experiences a decrease in performance achieves success and its goal. In this process, most of the organizations can go to bankruptcy. It is the task of the leaders to coordinate the harmony within the organization. Strategic management is an element that can be formed by the coordination of the individual carrying the leadership qualification as a whole, together with the organizational culture. The goals of the company must be created and analyzed with strategic formulas in the formation of future goals and values. Otherwise, not taking the activity of strategic planning to a strong side will cause the abandonment of the field of strategic planning. For this reason, since it will cost the companies to regress, not to progress, it is necessary for the management to move forward by being aware of each other together and in parallel with the lower top managers in the top management, and freedom of thought should be included in the internal organization culture. Organizations are associated with the formation of an indispensable period for the organization. Thus, the strategic mission of an organization with a high potential will be as high, and it will be a role model in making decisions within the organization. A charismatic leader is always at the forefront.

In addition to keeping it in the foreground, it is one of the most important and basic features of leadership and to listen carefully and motivate other employees' thoughts within the framework of respect. Under constant pressure and this disconnection in the upside-down relationship is a factor that causes failure because of that. The leader should know his responsibilities and if he desires responsibilities in a measured way according to the performance ratios of other employees in the distribution of duties, the success in the organization will increase. However, the employees whose ideas are not liked will be demotivated by insulting and degrading words and conveying them to the other side. For this reason, those with failure will lose the will to work, not being able to express their ideas, not being able to convey their talents to themselves and not being able to show their potential, employees who experience daily worries about the future will not want to put in any effort. This is a huge disappointment for the company. If one of the most successful basic elements of an institution is not known who is the leader when we enter an institution, we can definitely say that the organization is an institution with a strong strategy and a strong potential. He needs to play a big role in improving himself well, otherwise he sees himself as a leader and perceives other employees as low class, belittles their ideas and ignores their suggestions, and constantly dictates that they are either inadequate or unsuccessful by psychological pressure. are among the essentials. It is impossible to talk about the headache of an institution that has such a leadership qualification. Employees should be described as employees who have lost their self-confidence rather than motivation due to being constantly reprimanded because they cannot speak their minds out of fear or pressure. The leader is in the role of a captain, and although it is of course in the hands of the leader to direct where the ship will go and where it will not go, his employees have the right to determine a route. It is necessary to listen to the employees whose mission, that is, the future horizon, is clearly defined. The only truth is that the leader does not have a mindset and the employees should act by assuming that they think about the potential at least as much as the leaders. Of course,

there is no way to accept every thought and implement it or put it into production or service. But it needs to establish this bond between the employees very well, to convey to the employees that even the bad one will know how to fix what is right or wrong, and to guide the employees towards the good. It should be a kind of guide. If it proceeds in this way, the organization already has only one purpose. . To make its existence as sustainable as possible by gaining competitive advantage. This is both its mission and vision. The organizational ties between the organization and its employees are strengthened, and the leadership-dominant individual should be aware of this responsibility in order to take a step towards it. Otherwise, he achieved the leadership seat by using strategies in only one seat and under pressure, both by disturbing the peace within the organization and by applying psychological pressure by ignoring what the employees of the organization said. The individual, who thinks of himself as the top manager of the organization, never contributes to the organization. It does not provide any benefit to the institution it is in, and it can also invite negativities up to a decline in the competitive market by causing more harm than good. For this reason, companies should always aim at long-term goals in their strategies.

BETWEEN POWER AND LEADERSHIP ELEMENTS

The concept of leadership and power is characterized as a concept based on social foundations. In social life, a person must with both knowledge. In order for his ideas to be strong physically or mentally, this person should not be an introvert for once. Social activities and assertiveness may need to be more. In short, leadership printing should be identified with its own character. If there is such an individual, it means that the individual is strong. An individual whose thoughts and ideas are accepted without discussion within an organization within a society is said to have taken up the leadership quality. The decisions taken by these people are not questioned. In addition, because it brings attention, there is admiration for that person. For this reason, if the person who has leadership qualifications can effectively express the elements such as ethical and moral skills and talents and take the organizations under control, the word of that person is valued. When it comes to the issue of power resources, many distinctions mentioned in the leadership phenomenon can be combined with power resources. A leadership that can research and develop power sources and adapt to technological advances may be mentioned. The reason for this is, for example, if the leader in his business does not follow the technology and is not interested in the differences in the developing competitive market, he prefers to proceed at a constant level with a more traditional approach and I try to accept his ideas under pressure. There can be no talk of power sources here. .Because here a failure is mentioned here, a situation that is subject to a recession or to a stagnation. But and the leading research and development functions in his business follow very well. It follows the agenda, follows the technological developments in production, and develops it in self-education so that it can have the capacity to orientate the adaptation process to its organization, and this ensures that the situation of the enterprise is raised to the top level. We see that the company is capable of adapting its employees by following the technology and preparing trainings that will keep the adaptation process of the technological new development short . Because success

cannot be mentioned in an organization that has always been subjected to a fixed and traditionalist approach.

3.1.2. WHAT ATTITUDES OF THE LEADERS IN THE ORGANIZATION MAY CAUSE FAILURES

In accordance with the rules of leaders and their organization, they always appear as a department and a member of the department in the upper level. It is seen as a result of the most experienced name of the institution and the individual who is successful in terms of management. Top management is a difficult management system. Because as the head of the institution, I can do no harm, the stronger it is, the better the body will move. Its institution can also be exemplified as a human body. Any problem that occurs in the head region also negatively affects the body. The head depiction here belongs to the leader. Problems that may arise in the strategic analyzes and evaluations of the leader will increase the anxiety of the employees working in the organization. For this reason, the best way to make accurate analysis and research is to analyze the environmental factors of the organization very well. It is necessary to know the customers, suppliers and competitors well and to dominate the market. Namely, the market is a workbench built on supply and demand. For this, a strategic leader must integrate innovations and innovations into the organization as an idea to meet the expectations of the customers.

If strategic problems occur, it will affect the entire body direction. For this reason, while preparing a strategic roadmap, many leaders may experience negativity, namely failure, as a result of problems arising from their individual characteristics. This failure due to various reasons will negatively affect the organization. In the disruption of the organizations, the deficiencies in the product presentation in the market and the negativities there will have to be seen as a failed expense both in the environment and within the organization as the competitors overcome, this will cause the leader to experience a decline both individually and as a result of his duty.

First of all, it is an individual's overconfidence and ego expenditure. It is a chain of problems that arise from imagining an organizational system where everything he says is true and the thoughts of the employees are unimportant. Examples and results already make mistakes from the beginning by thinking that only their own knowledge and abilities are sufficient to solve the problems that occur in systems such as the organization. A leader who integrates only his own thoughts by ignoring the experiences of the employees has integrated his thoughts under pressure, which reduces the motivation of the employees. Of course, when the negativity occurs, the employees may take a stance against the leader. There is a culture called organizational culture on balance, so that there is incompatibility within the organization, so that the individual should not be overconfident. This is not just a form of strategy that targets the thoughts of the individual. It is the strategic alignment between employees and other individuals and their determination to achieve goals by putting their heads together.

3.2.1. RISKS AROUND THE ORGANIZATION AND THE LEADER'S DEFINITION OF THESE ELEMENTS

Being able to progress with understanding from a traditional point of view is a regressive result. As a result, a leading leader in the organization should be able to develop himself, adapt himself to the developing technologies, and convey his developments in this regard to his employees as well as the developing technologies are not only important for the leadership. Another way to be a charismatic leader is to take risks at the right place at the right time and to dominate the organization employees in this direction. In the world with developing technology, the stability and stagnation of a traditional organizational structure does not bring any gain to the organization. The leader must be dynamic and static. He must attach great importance to synergy. It is necessary to continue this way with individuals. It is known for always exhibiting an observant attitude in the eyes of the leader in the organization. This is a method that stems from the desire to keep the spirit of the team dynamic and young.

It is the leader's responsibility to enable them to adapt the technologies as soon as possible, this orientation, the elimination of problems and the production of solutions are the elements under the leader's responsibility. will lose.

3. As threats, they may encounter the problem of foresight. Because threats will always be around the business. This is a position related to the sustainability principle of the existence of the business and the business may not always make a profit. The forecasts of the business may not always go well, there will always be risks. But if the individual who is in fact ignores these signals, it means that he invites failure. For this reason, condoning or ignoring risks means that it affects the course of the business negatively. Organizations will definitely cause failure and the strategies created will not work. Because the luxury is great, there will be situations that cannot be overcome no matter how suitable the strategy. This is one of the mistakes that leaders have made out there.

4. In other words, not performing performance management in the enterprise is that assigning a task lower than the task quota that should be given to a high-performing individual within the enterprise or assigning a task to a low-performing person in a high quota will lead to organizational disconnections due to the imbalance in this responsibility and task distribution. In this way, organizations will be incomplete because talent management is not carried out regularly, and as a result, failure will follow.

5. Not to create the administrative concept of the strategy map that he has created himself. Because leaders, known as senior managers in businesses, have critical risks to be implemented when the strategy map is not created regularly, when decisions and targeted plans are not implemented, or when an extremely problematic decision is made. For this reason, one of the biggest reasons for not being able to meet the expectations of the business and the damage to the organizational culture is due to the regular execution of the strategic map. It is also known as an activity that influences success. Turkish management mentality needs to be updated. Every day, the world is developing very differently, and the progress of organizations is approached from a different perspective, so it is impossible for a leader to manage it alone. Successful leadership is only mentioned if it can be implemented in line with the

strategic analyzes and plans it has created, in short, if it does not have a problem in integrating knitting into Turkish culture. Otherwise, one can talk about an unsuccessful leadership.

3.2.2. MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS OF STRATEGIC LEADERSHIPS IN THE ORGANIZATION

Strategic leaders are divided into types within the class, they can be classified as directive and collaborative leader and visionary leadership. Visionary leadership is within the scope of future leadership processes with its sanctions and strategies within their own personal organizations, and it is the proactive and creative emergence of the perception required for the systems that form the basis of the priority organizational culture to achieve higher goals in order to provide competitive advantage in a system that adds to human resources. . In addition, guiding leadership, on the other hand, is called guiding leadership, which is to see and perceive the activities of the employees in the organization on their work on the vision and mission, to bring them to a better place and to provide them with a guiding stage in every aspect in order to reach the goals of the organization in a short time. These are to encourage their contribution to knitting by providing more alternative options and obtaining more divergent thinking. Collaborative leadership, on the other hand, is to adopt the common goals of the individuals working in different departments within the organization and the customer and competitive communities around the organization as a principle, first to define an environment, and then to make a large-scale research on how to meet the expectations of the customers in the organization. In this way, the effort to guide employees, customers, suppliers in order to achieve common goals is called collaborative leadership, but it is always useful to say that if an organization carries these three types of leaders above a single department, failure cannot be mentioned in that organization.

The reason for this is that the leader can achieve success only if the perspective as collaborative leadership or guiding or visionary leadership is one by one, but if he is talking about a leader who can integrate all three of them as a common goal to his employees and the organization, both environmental differences can be observed and the customer is the supplier and supplier. A leader who can control the organization is both known as a charismatic leader and employees adopt and care about these critical thinking styles, so it is one of the most basic features that can contribute to the development of a more beneficial and high-performing organization. A leader who can be a good guide with being able to be a good guide always achieves success. Naturally, risks and setbacks occur in the beginning. The most basic known feature is to be a visionary leader . Because there are people who would not want to come face to face with a strong leader. A strong leader takes risks. He knows that he will only take risks blindly or he will overcome it with alternative options. Thus , it is said that an individual who has the quality of a leader who follows the developments and environmental differences, can control the demands of all customers, whether they are shared, and who examines their demands and makes good researches that can meet their expectations from the company, is said to be a true captain of the ship. The basic functions of leadership provide a good framework analysis for the creation of performance models. All the arrangements it has created can be reviewed systematically. It must have a structure and the plans it has created in this dimension are sustainable. It is a plus for someone who is qualified to

have a relationship with the human resources department in order to include wage policies that can motivate employees. Because if they are constantly in the same place with a working person, even though their performance is high, they do not get promoted in any way, they prefer to keep their own work, if they have ideas and developments that will shed light on them. They never want to win. For this reason, by providing a good recipe system and a remuneration element, employees will provide more determination and stability if it is kept in the foreground that they can be overlooked with the sanctions that the employees are in return for their efforts. In this context, these contributions will automatically achieve a success that will affect the vision or mission of the enterprise. It has meaning as long as all the necessary foundations for it have been laid. For this reason, the promotion elements are determined by the leaders. Leaders determine the distribution of duties, and by determining the wage policies with the strategy they have created together with human resources, high-performing employees receive high salaries. In this way, a prestige is gained in the organization. No one will want to leave that place of work and organization, and they will not want to go to a job where there is a strong strategy in the workplace and an orientation of the organization. For some reason, high success can be achieved with these contributions. Not only that, the individual who is a leader gains more prestige and strengthens his position at the top by revealing performance models thanks to strong criteria. It also ensures that the individuals working in horses coordinate their work.

3.3.1. ELEMENTS OF A STRATEGIC CHARISMATIC LEADER WITHIN THE ORGANIZATION

Another element of strategic leadership is that they should form the basis of their shaping within all organizations. Because it is necessary to accept what the strategic leader says in a difficult and charismatic way in the organization in order to be able to prevent girls in the future. By encouraging this, it is an element of effort to provide reinforcements within the organization by making rewards among employees or by ensuring that premium salaries are received more. At the same time, it should be encouraged to work. It is a very important factor for employees to follow the developing technologies in order to gain a global competitive advantage in order to meet the expectations. It is a very important element that the organization should not be seen as just an organization, but that it sees some and continues to work as a team.

Otherwise, the expectations of the business will not be met . Bankruptcy becomes inevitable.

Motivation and performance development trainings should be prepared. This is an element of a good strategic leader. Otherwise, employees are made dependent on leaving a traditional organization. This is also a very boring cycle, because employees cannot get paid for their efforts and experience adaptation problems with developing technology. They may not want to work in an organization where they have problems in developing and expressing themselves, so they follow what the leader says and decide to leave the organization by resigning, naturally many job seekers in the market will not want to work in this organization because of a very high dismissal rate. No one will want to work in a company with a

low production capacity and an organization that has a problem of adapting to technological developments. The damage to the trust in the organization will enable to exist in a cycle that will contribute to the progress of the negative points. The strategic leader must first determine the extent and rate of production and service. You can achieve this thanks to market impressions. Namely, it is an element that can be started by taking the step found by hiring the necessary and coordinated qualified personnel. They have to learn the systems in other foreign companies by organizing many trips. Thanks to the researches on how to obtain these in our country, they can enable the emergence of new markets. They cannot achieve this by simply advancing in the market they are in or with a traditionalist approach. To achieve this, they must open up to the outside. They can achieve this through their research and development functions, by participating in the necessary exhibitions and business meetings abroad, and by making the best advertisements of their organizations. Accordingly, they need to know very well how superior they can be to rival markets and what happens to their vision and mission. In short, he needs to know the environment well. A leader who knows the environment well knows very well where to take the first step. Otherwise, if the organization for recognizing the environment departs with its own thoughts and products, the ship will sink. Because the person you call the captain is the leader alone, responsible for creating a strategy that can best determine the route. For this reason, the employees will decide to leave the organization as soon as they see the course of the ship and that the ship will sink. Most likely, this result will bring a chain of negativities. Because recovery will take a lot of time, a well-established enterprise will not be destroyed easily. If this is a business that has a strong vision and mission and knows the competitor's environment very well, it should add strength to its strength, along with customers perhaps need to know the rappers' expectations. Because the business environment is a demand and supply-oriented environment, if it fails as a result of researches and assignments on what the demand is and what the expectations are, and how it will be the best, it is the leader's duty to repair it as soon as possible. By providing a motivation process again, it is our duty to ensure that the employees do not give up, not to spread, not to be negative, by touting that the organization has strong foundations and that they can overcome this situation as long as they are united in every way. If the negativities in the structure of the organization blame each other or put pressure on the employees and shut them down in activities that psychologically water them completely, the recovery process will decrease, that is, this organization will not be able to move forward. The ship that goes with a successful strategy will not sink, so nothing will happen to the employees. are task functions. The leader has a burden of responsibility to coordinate all this. It is very important to know the basics of these responsibilities well and to take the right steps and make the right decisions. It should not be individualistic. If it has a selfish nature, employees cannot express their opinions and communication gaps are ensured. This causes the tension within the organization to rise. If a harmonious environment is desired, the ideas must be well coordinated and expressed in a free environment. Independence within the organization is important. But commitment to the organization is even more important. Mutual respect and honesty are not very qualified behaviors in order to lay the foundations of commitment within the organization. Because when this behavior comes together, it also reflects on the environment, and a happy organization means a happy customer. Incompatibilities within the organization will also be reflected in the production process. Customers will lose their preference with the system in terms of

setbacks in the production process, inability to meet demand, or inability to innovate. These are some of the factors that cause negative effects on the company. In short, the strategic leader should be well aware of his task responsibilities and ensure that they provide motivation and performance coordination very well within himself. Today, many short-skinned leaders with their egos come to a high level and want to keep themselves in the foreground by oppressing and bullying their subordinates. This is one of the negative places in the production process in the organization. If the employees cannot show their success in a company and their potential is not properly distributed, of course, failure can be mentioned in this case. With the loss of prestige of the establishment, these conflicts occur within it.

If a leader who is called serious is defined as the highest authority after the managerial qualification of the organization, he must act with a team spirit. Risks are taken in the name of innovations that may occur. These risks can bring both positive and negative consequences. But if the team can be motivated and overcome the individuals and the long-term goals can be achieved in the shortest time, it shows that the sales analysis is really strong. Because managing and taking responsibility is a skin quality to act with team spirit. This does not bind employees, but their sincerity and loyalty to the organization that binds them. Also, their thoughts on reaching the goals are their assistants and efforts. It's your and only responsibility. Being a leader is not an easy thing. He is an individual who lives a stressful and busy duty life. He should not only see himself as a leader, but also as a team employee. Strategy and leadership can be overwhelming. For this reason, the organization's employees will be more motivated if they take into account the thoughts of other employees as well as their own thoughts, not by rebuffing the thoughts that do not make their minds, but by pulling them to the positive side with a better language, for example, by completing them with motivating words such as "It would be better if we did this as well." and takes an even stronger approach. Because the advice given by the leader of the organization ensures that his ideas can be put into practice. Otherwise, no one will want to work under the same roof with a leader who does not care about thoughts, a leader who does not like ideas, and a leader who resents. Even if he is working out of necessity, no one wants to work in this company because the success rate of medicine is falling, or he can recover when he leaves this company. It is true that it is very important that the organization distributes tasks according to the training they have received and the experiences they have gained while the organization distributes the tasks so that all these do not occur. Otherwise, automatically assigning a customer representative to someone who does not speak a foreign language is the biggest mistake he can make, or to employ someone who knows a foreign language and has experience in this field in smaller jobs, even making the project work again, is a great waste of time and a great loss of time for him in the organization. It is the beginning of conflict. In order for all these not to happen, he must first know the individuals. Since each of the individuals in the team is taken into the team, it is considered that they have a certain talent. If it looks like a wide field, a work should be seen as football on the main field, putting the best players in the foreground and placing other people with lower potential as supportive staff is one of the best decisions a strategic leader can make. determined as a function. Namely, the main purpose of strategic leadership is to see the future, to predict the future. There is never a risk-free environment in the future. However, one of the important elements for the revamidi of the organizations is to create a barrier with the strategies it has created in order to get the best card against tsunamis that may occur, with strong predictive power. The organization needs

to be protected against external factors. If such a strong leader is in the organization, the employees will be really impressed. Because the employees will want to be like him, and they will strictly follow what he says and the managerial policies he has created, and they will see him as a local leader. This allows the synergy within the organization to be strengthened and it is an element that increases the efforts and successes of its personnel, which strengthens them. When strong and non-solid leadership is combined with important facts, a moment can be established by taking strong steps, otherwise problems will be experienced not only in the realization of the goals, but even in the chain of command within the organization.

3.3.2. ARE THE LEADER & EXECUTIVE FUNCTIONAL THE SAME CONCEPTS?

Leadership is often confused with what we call managers, but there is a big difference between leaders and managers. Leaders focus on the goals, while the managers are thinking about achieving the goals of the backward organization. The vision and mission of the organization, how high its production volume should be and how high the value of the organization should be in the competition market, while the authority to fulfill the responsibilities against the efforts in these matters ensures the protection of the system, while the manager can only make a sanction against the authority consisting of the position he/she has. Leaders, on the other hand, are managers who often follow them and take on tasks that require compliance with them, only they can intervene as long as they allow their professional positions. I am always aware of the fact that I have a duty and responsibilities towards the environment and the individuals who follow them, namely the employees in the organization, and while undertaking these responsibilities, managers often value being responsible to the organization.

In short, leaders assume twice as much responsibility. According to the managers, that is, the leaders were managers . Managers are not leaders. Both are individuals who carry out tasks in different elements. Leadership is an element that requires more responsibility. The manager, who must be aware of the interactions of the systems, who must be aware of the interactions and transfer his knowledge and experience about them to the activities of all activities both inside and outside the organization, is limited only to the position he/she is in within the organization. Both of his responsibilities are never the same. is a type of word. Namely, since ancient times, human beings have been in search of a leader after they started to live in groups. Whenever there was a need for an individual who managed the society, coordinated the society and ensured unity. In short, organizations need a leader who can coordinate them, motivate them and be empowered, just like individuals in the ancient society. Thus, the phenomenon of leadership has come from history to the present. However, there is an element that every leader is not sufficient for every organization and may not be considered sufficient. Employees may not want to work as a leader who does not take enough responsibility and does not have a strong strategy. This is an element that regresses the organization rather than success. The leaders we call charismatic leaders are strong leaders. However, if we talk about a leader in a traditional structure, this charismatic leader is more passive and does not advance the organization. It cannot over-integrate its own developer elements. Because it has a traditional structure, it wants to progress in stable conditions. However, as

the modern world turns, technology is advancing as the modern world turns. The leader needs to research all these developments closely.

It is a very important issue that organizations should act in a structure that is open to national values education and develop themselves, and that no one should implement their plans under pressure. Because, of course, strategy is a system that will create a route, he said, and his mission. However, if it integrates it in the best way by creating a synergy force by creating a gift in a team spirit, success will come by itself. Employees will spontaneously increase their desire and a desire to contribute more will arise. There is a unity of forces in an organization where we are not a selfish structure, otherwise this leader is doing this selfish and invites failure by succumbing to his ego. In order to prevent this, he should not know that the phenomenon of leadership consists only of office and seat. Leadership is also the head of the organization. It is a science that also examines the social areas opened administratively. Because it analyzes the expectations of the society formed by the management systems in the analyzes that deal with and do with the customer and supplier environment . It analyzes the production of its own organizations and to what extent it meets the demands and ensures that it takes its place in the competitive market accordingly. Otherwise, he will have undertaken the failures as well as the collapses. It can be said that leaders are an important factor in opening new doors and increasing productivity with new perspective thoughts. A leader is always responsible for bringing innovations to the organization that will affect performance. Having the opportunity to get to know the environment better by organizing non-profit organizations, organizing trips and participating in fairs are among the main ones . They prepare a roadmap thanks to the analyzes used to confirm what mistakes they made or what strategies they developed. Thanks to this strategic roadmap, the business will get to know the institution and its missions, and the uncertainties will be eliminated. Of course, this way, the top managers will be able to make better decisions, and as a result of this decision, the employees will be happy and more performance and efficiency will be gained. In the first place, there should be no pressure in the strategic structure of the individual with the leadership feature they have created. It is very important to have smooth and flexible ethics in their plans and millions so that they can integrate well with employees. Because the more positive the environment and the stronger the synergy.

He needs to make important analyzes such as being able to see the future, predict and know the weaknesses or strengths in these predictions. It is always necessary to care about the opinions of other employees. Because employees who work in an environment where their thoughts are not listened to may be hesitant to present their ideas and maybe their ideas will contribute to the organization. However, because they cannot cope with the oppressive and egoistic attitude of the leader, they prefer to stay in the background and stay in the passive background, which does more harm to the organization than gain. It needs to be assertive in the competitive market in environmental situations. A strong charismatic leader needs to attract attention with his courage in order to attract more the current of thought of the employees in the organization. Of course, it is important that this courage is not an empty one. A courage that can handle the burden of responsibility acting with a sense of duty is good. It is necessary to organize and integrate the knowledge gained through experience to the employees in the organization in a short time.

4.1. TAKING STRATEGIC ANALYSIS IN A CYCLICAL PERSPECTIVE

First of all, one of the basic elements that should be created in the strategic map is what is desired? How does bringing the desired position in the company shape the vision and mission? How can we reach our strategic goal in a shorter time and with success? In order to search for answers to the questions in the form, three target lists should be created. In these target lists, first of all, the location and purpose that the organization wants to reach should be included. It is a very important element to emphasize what the knowledge they have, that is, the values, should be in order to achieve this goal. Next comes the mission. After the creation of the goals and values, the extent to which the mission targeted by the organization should be is a situation that can be created together with the analysis. While creating this situation, the prestige of the company, the organization, and the identity of the organization should be kept in the foreground. Who are we and who are we for? what are we producing? how much do we produce As long as the plans in these processes are analyzed and created well, the desired position is entered. In addition, SWOT analysis is performed. With adjective analysis, risks, opportunities, threats and many points that can be developed are identified and alternative solutions can be revealed. Together with these alternative processes, a strategic choice is created, then implemented, and after being implemented, it is strategically eliminated from a control mechanism and presented to the customer. Here's how I explained how this topic starts with the cyclical creation of strategic planning, goals, the environmental organization's own identity profile, when all of these come together, SWOT analysis and whether it can be created, alternative solution or the development of the issues to be developed, together with them by classifying them as strategic determination, selection, implementation and control mechanism. SWOT analysis is useful in measuring the skills and abilities of organizations. It has benefits such as not missing the opportunities that will occur in achieving success and ensuring that the threats are completely resolved with alternative options as soon as possible. But before these, strategic analyzes come first and then environmental analysis. It should never be forgotten that the environmental factor has a very important place in the creation of these successful mission and vision systems, which will be handled proactively and objectively. It should know the environment somewhere and environmental strategies should be created. The strategic plans within the organization may well be future-oriented. However, the strategic plans for the environment determine how much risks the supplier and the market will face the company, which may occur according to these, to the customer.

4.2.STRATEGIC SELECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION PROCESSES

After all these analyzes are made for the strategic, after the SWOT analysis, alternative developments or something are created, an election system is now passed, and the final decision is expected to be made by senior executives who are competent in a strategic selection part in planning, and this final decision is also evaluated. For example, if the assistant manager responsible for a marketing department achieves

sales success directly, he does not approve of other sales systems. Because if the telephone sales part generates more income, send it, for this reason, it includes these marketing systems to a high degree by going to someone's feet, not mobile, but by promoting it via phone or website, and this choice is applied as a strategic choice.

Of course, the creation of these elections cannot be ignored, the evaluations that occur in their systems are added to the target list after an extremely detailed filtering, and after the decision is delivered, senior managers classify them in order to eliminate other possible errors on a regular basis. The practice is the continuation of the company's actually produced activities, that is, their daily sales were no longer door-to-door or with a promotional tool, they continue their activities by promoting their activities via phone or website. Then, of course, after creating these, the last stage is control. It is a process that helps to determine whether all environmental factors, quality controls in the production of products within the company and the systematic strategic selection factors that have changed recently, have increased by considering all these and whether the company has reached a certain level. an audit at the same time because the implemented stages definitely need a control at the end . Finally, the vendor determines the control system.

4.3. THE ANSWER TO THE QUESTION LEADERS SEARCH WHILE CREATING STRATEGIC ANALYSIS

After a leader obtains strategic analyzes and evaluations, the company determines the profile of the firm and must answer the question of what its competencies are in this profile. We are an organization with production capacity and competence in which field? Also, what can we do with our resources? It analyzes for a company both in terms of quantity and quality in order to find answers to questions such as how we can cope with our competitors in the current market.

He examines the performance of individuals in the firm and is obsessed with the extent to which they can benefit to achieve success in accordance with the estimated capacity. It also tries to find the best for the organization with a predictable roadmap by making a comparison among the competitors. Regardless of the desire, the performance ratio of all employees in production is high, the supporting role in contributing to the production and the rise of the organization is the responsibility of the strategic leadership. But these are not situations that can happen to the same extent. During this analysis, of course, there is a decrease. Because not every individual has received the same education. It is not the same experience. In order to strengthen production, it is necessary to accelerate the adaptation processes of the individuals left behind to work as soon as possible. It needs to integrate the strategic plans that it has created by separating it and taking it as a whole. If this is transferred to the employees with a plan and definition that can keep the synergy in the organization strong, a strong and intelligent leader can be divorced, some success can be mentioned here. He understood the answer to this question through his analysis. It is concluded that he knew how to deal with his opponents, how to strengthen his abilities

and keep them in the foreground. While businesses define group profiles with various analyzes, they can achieve success by closely monitoring and defining the leader profiles.

They have taken the steps of strategic planning. Realizing that the company's performance capability has also increased, the leader has coordinated both financial and evaluations on this issue and contributes to the management. A successful coordination is required for a successful production. Thanks to the harmony and motivation unity created within the organization, it brings a situation related to the quality of the production rather than the production capacity of this product. If there is an organization with high performance and high efficiency, it is said that the production is good. With such organizations, the leader can get to know the organization better and make preliminary plans for both employees and environmental analyzes. The leader can present a map of strategic goals and values to the managers with the goals he has created for the future of the organization. Organizations are made by targeting achievements that bring success in the short term but can last in the long term. First, a mission is determined. The goal is created, the goal is created, analyzed, and alternative evaluations are made and selected. After it has been processed, the organization came to it by checking and making analyzes and comparisons between other competing companies as the last step.

It also has the problematic task of informing managers, suppliers, buyers and entrepreneurs, or observing competitors directly. It is one of the elements that strengthens the strategy that the leader has created, to do these things closely and in a way that is constantly updated . The fact that a few of them have been disrupted causes the plan to return to the beginning. For this reason, in order to continue the plan without interruption, it needs to coordinate alternative systems more and more every day. It can attract the attention of customers by organizing events. These are non-profit organizations. The customer is impressed and the employees are motivated and encouraged. For example, charismatic leaders are important in strategic planning in terms of creating these non-profit organizations, that is, those that will come together, and this does not come together, both for the customer to get to know the organization better and for the organization to create elements that can increase the prestige. Contrary to expectations, the business world will feature both positive and negative aspects, but the organization should never compromise its philosophy when these negative aspects are experienced. Its protection within the organization is very important. True, a person dispersed in a small concussion is already doomed to disintegration because there is no strong strategic leadership. they will arrive in time. Therefore, at the beginning of all the ways to success, organizational culture and leadership forces should be able to create a kind of route and transport the ship to the port in the best possible way in a short time and without any passengers getting injured.

5.1. STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP OF MUSTAFA KEMAL ATATÜRK

Talking only about leadership within the organization limits the qualification of leadership. However, talking about the strategic leadership of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk is a suitable term for a universal

definition of leadership. Mustafa Kemal Atatürk is the commander-in-chief that comes to mind in history when it comes to strategic leadership. It has been seen once again what a charismatic leader he is, since he manages the phenomenon of the state as if he manages an organization and motivates the individuals in the war to achieve success in the war at the expense of their lives. We have witnessed in history that although we are many times less than the enemy soldiers against the country, with a strong philosophy, our country did not allow them to seize its lands.

This means that no matter how few people work in an organization, it has shown us that nothing can be done without motivation. After the philosophy and strategic map is created by analyzing correctly, both the state, the army and the organization will reach their goals in a short time. We have seen since history that it will never be defeated and will stand upright. Atatürk has always been a strategic leader and has evaluations. This goal has emerged with analyzes and analyzes as a result of quantitative research in Antalya. As the leader of the Republic of Turkey, Mustafa Kemal Atatürk once again shows us how his leadership has come a long way with strategic developments in the past. If we consider the situation in the country, an example can be given to resurrect the consonant, revitalize the established branches and bring them back to life. Mustafa Kemal Atatürk was a leader who had all the expenses listed for himself. Undoubtedly, your strategic management in war has been proven by the soldiers. Whether with his ideas, analyzes, thoughts or foresights, he was the only leader at that time who best demonstrated his increasing strategic planning to the Turkish army, which had low ammunition in the war.

5.2.JUL CAESAR'S STRATEGIC LEADERSHIP AND COMMAND

Although Caesar is known as the leader at the head of the Roman Empire, he protected his country by showing a great command success in the military sense. To give an example, be it the Gallic wars and the civil wars of the novel, he achieved serious success with his well-formed strategy.

Caesar has always kept the infantry and water data in one class, and in this way he kept up with the difficult course of the Roman empires. With a strong persuasiveness and strategic leadership, he always kept the infantry and cavalry, that is, the army he created, at the forefront compared to other armies and motivated their success to progress. has been laid. Thanks to Caesar, he proved how important strategic management is in the fifth century BC and that the command can move forward with plans and these motivations. It can be said that he was a complete strategy planning expert. The reason for this is that he embraces his soldiers and his country instead of them, and he knows that the foundations of a strong civilization with these possessions are based on a strong leadership. A good bureaucracy and his superior success in wars by motivating and motivating his people reveals that Caesar is an expert in strategy without a doubt. At the same time, I see more successes related to the Egyptian economy. Certification systems have also achieved success on a separate level. Today, if Caesar can still speak at the beginning of the Roman Empire and his power and victory over Gaul can be talked about, we can see how a correct strategy has progressed today. Otherwise, Caesar is not talked about as much as other emperors. The reason for its increase in popularity is that it has achieved great success by motivating and encouraging

its army, as well as having a good command. It is a responsible position that undertakes the goals of the organization. It is inevitable that individuals with a high research and analysis capacity will prefer this task. Because the leader should be someone who knows that he can only achieve success if he puts his ego aside and acts as if he is a member of the organization. We have seen that it is a very important element for the organization to have an authority that can be trained in every field, think flexibly and control the synergy within the organization. This will cause conflicts within the organization and the organization must be empty. If problems such as fights, internal conflicts, position fights, such thoughts, unrest within the organization and problems such as not fulfilling the authority in the distribution of duties occur, the main goal will not be achieved. Coordinating them is also one of the strategic elements of the organizations in the systems of motivating the employees and rewarding them according to their performance. The organization should focus only on the target and act as a team. It is the leader's responsibility to fulfill the mandate and keep this synergy under control.

He or she would be interested only in the competitive market where there are conflicts of interest. However, in an organization where it is not given much importance, progress cannot be made, on the contrary, regression is spent. The organization must be in a team spirit in order to recover from negativities in a short time. An organization that does not have a team spirit content can not recover even if it takes a long time to recover. Because the individuals in the organization are free from each other, they cannot carry out their duties properly, naturally, no matter how well you plan the strategy, actions are negative as long as they are not implemented as long as they are not implemented. Negative is as if it was never created. Being always is an incentive for the organization to be able to overcome even uncoordinated problems. For this reason, the strategic leader is also the charismatic leader of the organization. Individuals in the organization should be inspired by themselves. In this inspirational time, he is seen as a leader who has passed the stage of accepting his thoughts. A leader who respects the opinions of the employees and can put forward thoughts and ideas that invest in the future in order to coordinate the motivation within the organization has completely won. Information on the subject should be updated within the organization. Strong analysis lays the foundation of a strong leader because he is not just a position but also a pilot of an airplane. Everyone's life and safety is responsible for him until he lands the plane under his management and responsibility safely. Just as a pilot is able to make a healthy landing despite all kinds of bad weather conditions that may occur, his experience shows his strategic predictability and success. However, it is of great importance for a novice pilot or a pilot who cannot use his powers properly, to panic and decide quickly and strategically whether it is better to land in the right place or in the middle of the ocean despite the weather conditions. This is due to how inexperienced the pilot is and

it indicates that he is inexperienced, therefore, as in the example given, there is no difference between the pilot and the strategic leader, that is, the leader at the beginning of the establishment. The aim and focus seem to be achieving success in both.

In short, being a leader is a very difficult profession rather than being a manager. Rather than a profession or position, individuals who can take steps together by shouldering the entire burden of the organization, are open to the outside world in terms of self-education and develop developmentally and have strong research and development functions should take this task. Otherwise, the competitive

market is very tough. It is a market and not everyone can achieve this. An individual who can analyze and think objectively, constantly updates these developments, is experienced in strategy planning and strategic map creation, and can motivate the organization, must carry the flag.

6.Results

When it comes to strategy, the first thing that comes to our mind is to reach the goal in a short time and with the right steps through a plan or project. This means that all these achievements gathered within the organization or organizations are progressing with the right steps and on the right path, a situation that can show a separate ability and talent. It is of great importance that the ideas are formed correctly in order to create the future success and motivation of the company or an organization. In the organization, the strategy is not only about the mission and mission. At the same time, the leader uses the pressure to motivate the personnel more quickly where necessary, and to eliminate the disconnection in the lower and upper units in the work, in order to achieve the targeted qualifications of the task responsibilities. It is the first duty in the leader's plans to ensure that the success within the organization is kept at a measured rate. The second element is to shorten the adaptation period to the next technologies. For example, when a new employee encounters programs and procedures that he/she does not know, he/she may inevitably have a tendency to withdraw from his/her work. But a strong and charismatic leader must always keep all negativities and possibilities under control. Otherwise, the imbalance in the education rate indicates that an element will focus more and have more problems with your value.

Leadership can only become a whole with strategy. Management is a system that requires heavy responsibility and has difficulties in the distribution of tasks. It is difficult to keep this system alive. Therefore , the difference between the chairman of the board of directors and the leader emerges. Leadership is always more difficult and tiring. Important functions that require leadership should be an individual who has leadership qualities and is open to education. This is very important for the changing synergy to permeate the organization.

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